

РАЗДЕЛ. ЕСТЕСТВЕННЫЕ НАУКИ

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7654157>
UOT 547.372

**STUDY OF PROPYLENE CATALYTIC OXIDATION PROCESS
IN A FLOW-TYPE TUBULAR REACTOR**

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Annotation: The effect of partial pressure and contact time on the oxidation process of propylene in zinc-vanadium oxide catalyst samples was studied in a flow-type tubular reactor and the optimal conditions were determined. It was shown that propylene oxidation products in the taken catalyst samples consist of acetic acid, carbon dioxide, acetone and acetaldehyde. Based on the obtained results, the effect of partial pressure of propylene, oxygen, water vapor and contact time on the oxidation process of propylene was studied in order to determine the optimal oxidation conditions of propylene in the indicated catalyst. The oxidation of olefins in the liquid and gas phase is based on obtaining a number of target and intermediate products with the participation of various binary catalysts. The oxidation of propylene, which is an example of olefins, in the liquid phase involves the oxidation of titanium and its alloys with molecular oxygen on the contact surfaces of this catalyst. The highest form of oxidation of olefins in the gas phase is catalyst indicates molybdenum, cobalt, iron, bismuth, antimony and silicon oxides. One of the catalytic oxidation products of propylene is acetic acid.

Keywords: propylene, acetic acid, oxidation, binary catalysts, acetone, acetaldehyde, reactor, partial pressure, contact time, etc

ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ ПРОЦЕССА КАТАЛИТИЧЕСКОГО ОКИСЛЕНИЯ ПРОПИЛЕНА В ПРОТОЧНОМ ТРУБЧАТОМ РЕАКТОРЕ

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Аннотация: Исследовано влияние парциального давления и времени контакта на процесс окисления пропилена в образцах цинк-ванадиевого катализатора в трубчатом реакторе проточного типа и определены оптимальные условия. Показано, что продукты окисления пропилена в отобранных образцах катализатора состоят из уксусной кислоты, диоксида углерода, ацетона и ацетальдегида. На основании полученных результатов было изучено влияние парциального давления пропилена, кислорода, паров воды и времени контакта на процесс окисления пропилена с целью определения оптимальных условий окисления пропилена в указанном катализаторе. Окисление олефинов в жидкой и газовой фазе основано на получении ряда целевых и промежуточных продуктов с участием различных бинарных катализаторов. Окисление пропилена, являющегося примером олефинов, в жидкой фазе включает окисление титана и его сплавов молекулярным кислородом на контактных поверхностях этого катализатора. Высшей формой окисления олефинов в газовой фазе является катализатор, указывающий на оксиды молибдена, кобальта, железа, висмута, сурьмы и кремния. Одним из продуктов каталитического окисления пропилена является уксусная кислота.

Ключевые слова: пропилен, уксусная кислота, окисление, бинарные катализаторы, ацетон, ацетальдегид, реактор, парциальное давление, время контакта и др

Acetic acid is one of the main monomers used in the petrochemical industry [1, 2]. Acetic acid is obtained in different ways. Various simple and complex catalysts have been proposed for this reaction. Catalysts based on vanadium oxide show high activity in the oxidation of olefins to acetic acid [3, 4]. It is also known that catalysts based on tin oxide have high activity in the oxidation of butylene to acetic acid [5, 6]. Taking into account the above, the optimal conditions of the oxidation process of propylene in various tin-vanadium-oxide catalyst samples in a flow-type reactor were studied. The oxidation process of propylene in different tin-vanadium-oxide catalyst samples was studied in the temperature range of 150 0 C-450 0 C. In order to determine the optimal oxidation conditions of propylene in the specified catalyst, we have studied the effect of partial pressure of propylene, oxygen, water vapor and contact time on the oxidation process of propylene.

The effect of partial pressure of propylene on the oxidation process to acetic acid was studied at a volume rate of 1200 h⁻¹ of the reaction mixture. The partial pressure of oxygen was kept at 0.1 atm., and the partial pressure of water vapor at 0.40 atm. The partial pressure of propylene varies between 0.025-0.200 atm. The contact time is kept constant by feeding the reaction mixture with the required amount of nitrogen. The influence of the partial pressure of propylene on the rate of conversion of propylene to acetic acid, acetone and carbon dioxide, the oxidation selectivity of propylene to acetic acid and the conversion of propylene is shown in Figure 1.

By increasing the partial pressure of propylene, the degree of conversion to acetic acid decreases. So, propylene at a temperature of 300 0 C is 0.025 atm. while the yield of acetic acid at partial pressure is 48.8 %, 0.20 atm. the yield of acetic acid at partial pressure is 15.6 %. Increasing the partial pressure of propylene also leads to a decrease in the viscosity of acetone (it decreases from 7.3 % to 0 % at a temperature of 300 0 C).

As the partial pressure of propylene increases, the output of carbon dioxide decreases as well as other reaction products. The oxidation selectivity of propylene to acetic acid increases with increasing partial pressure of propylene. This shows that increasing the partial pressure of propylene manifests itself more in the oxidation of propylene to acetic acid. Perhaps, increasing the partial pressure of propylene in the reaction mixture begins to adsorb propylene in other centers that respond to side reaction oxidation.

Increasing the partial pressure of propylene leads to a decrease in its conversion. The effect of partial pressure of oxygen on the oxidation process of propylene was studied at a volume rate of 1200 h⁻¹ of the reaction mixture. The partial pressure of propylene is 0.05 atm., and the partial pressure of water vapor is 0.40 atm. has been kept. The partial pressure of oxygen from 0.0 to 0.3 atm. varies between As can be seen from Figure 2, increasing the partial pressure of oxygen leads to a decrease in the degree of conversion of propylene to acetone. The degree of oxidation of propylene to acetone at 300 0 C is equal to 3.5 % and decreases to zero with an increase in the partial pressure of oxygen. In contrast to the rate of conversion of propylene to acetone, the yield of acetic acid increases initially with the increase of partial pressure of oxygen. Thus, increasing the partial pressure from 0.025 to 0.15 atm. at 300 0 C leads to an increase in the yield of acetic acid from 20 to 31.0 %, and then it begins to decrease, as well as the rate of conversion of propylene to carbon dioxide with oxygen increases with the increase of partial pressure. The partial pressure of oxygen is 0.2 atm. at a temperature of 300 0 C, the release of carbon dioxide is equal to 20.5 %.

The oxidation selectivity of propylene to acetic acid passes through the maximum as a result of the increase in the rate of conversion of propylene to by-products (carbon dioxide) by increasing the partial pressure of oxygen. Thus, at a temperature of 300 0 C, the maximum oxidation selectivity of propylene to acetic acid is 72 %. Thus, increasing the partial pressure of oxygen leads to the destructive oxidation of propylene to acetic acid and carbon dioxide, thereby reducing the oxidation selectivity of propylene to acetic acid effect of water vapor at a volume rate of 1200 h⁻¹ of the reaction mixture was studied. The partial pressure of propylene and oxygen was kept constant – 0.025 atm. The partial pressure of water vapor was changed from 0.0 to 0.7 atm. The contact time was kept constant by supplying the required amount of nitrogen to the reaction mixture. The effect of partial pressure of water vapor on the degree of conversion of propylene to acetic acid, acetone and carbon dioxide, as well as on the conversion of propylene and oxidation selectivity to acetic acid is shown in Fig. 3. In the absence of water vapor, only deep oxidation of propylene to acetic acid and carbon dioxide is observed. As it can be seen, by increasing the partial pressure of water vapor, the degree of conversion of propylene to acetic acid increases up to 29.5 % at a temperature of 300 0 C. A subsequent increase in the partial pressure of water vapor leads to a decrease in the yield of acetic acid per given propylene. At higher

temperatures, the effect of water vapor is stronger. The conversion rate of propylene into acetone and acetaldehyde also exceeds the maximum. The partial pressure of water vapor is 0.20 atm. raising it up leads to an increase in acetone and acetaldehyde. The partial pressure is 0.20 – 0.35 atm. water vapor has almost no effect on the degree of conversion of propylene in the interval. The subsequent increase in the partial pressure of water vapor leads to a decrease in the yield of other reaction products. To the maximum yield of acetic acid (29.5 %), at a temperature of 300 0 C and a partial pressure of water vapor of 0.40 atm. is achieved when unlike the oxidation of propylene to acetic acid and acetone, increasing the partial pressure of water vapor leads to a monotonically decreasing rate of conversion of propylene to carbon dioxide. Thus, increasing the partial pressure of water vapor at a temperature of 300 0 C leads to a decrease in the degree of conversion of propylene to carbon dioxide (from 8.6 to 5.2 %).

Figure 1 – Effect of partial pressure of propylene on the oxidation process at 300°C; (1 – Oxidation selectivity of propylene to acetic acid; 2 – Selectivity of propylene; 3 – Extraction of acetic acid; 4 – Emission of carbon dioxide; 5 – Extraction of acetone)

Figure 2 – Effect of oxygen partial pressure on propylene oxidation process at 300°C; (1 – Oxidation selectivity of propylene to acetic acid; 2 – Conversion of propylene; 3 – Derivation of acetic acid; 4 – Carbon dioxide emission; 5 – Deduction of acetone)

Figure 3 – Effect of water vapor partial pressure on propylene oxidation process at 300 °C; (1 – Oxidation selectivity of propylene to acetic acid; 2 – propylene conversion; 3 – extraction of acetic acid; 4 – release of carbon dioxide; 5 – derivation of acetone)

Figure 4 – Effect of contact time on the oxidation process of propylene (1 – Oxidation selectivity of propylene to acetic acid; 2 – Conversion of propylene; 3 – Extraction of acetic acid; 4 – Release of carbon dioxide; 5 – Derivation of acetone)

Water vapor increases the oxidation selectivity of propylene to acetic acid. Increasing the partial pressure of water vapor increases the oxidation selectivity of propylene from 67 % to 80 %, as shown in Figure 3. Water vapor has a positive effect on the conversion of propylene. Increasing the partial pressure of water vapor up to 0.5 atm. increases the conversion of propylene up to 45 %. as it is due to competitive adsorption of water vapor. Based on the above, it can be said that water vapor increases the overall conversion of propylene and at the same time slows down its complete oxidation, that is, water vapor has a positive effect on the oxidation of propylene to acetic acid.

The influence of the contact time on the activity of the tin-vanadium oxide catalyst was investigated by changing the amount of the catalyst in the reactor. The contact time varies from 0.0 to 5. Figure 4 shows the effect of contact time on the degree of conversion of propylene to acetic acid, acetone and carbon dioxide, propylene conversion and oxidation selectivity to acetic acid. When the contact time is 1 second, propylene is oxidized to acetic acid at 200 0 C. At this temperature, propylene is oxidized to acetic acid with 100 % selectivity and 7 % yield. Carbon dioxide and acetone begin to form at a temperature of 220 0 C. It

can be seen from Figure 4 that by increasing the contact time at low temperature, the yield of acetone and the selectivity for acetone increase, and at high temperature, it passes the maximum, and the yield of carbon dioxide and acetic acid increases [7-8].

Table 1 – Results of the oxidation process of propylene to acetic acid under the given conditions

Temperature	220	320
Pressure	atmosphere	atmosphere
Volumetric rate of the reaction mixture, hour ⁻¹	1500	1500
Propylene:air:water vapor, mole ratio	1:8:4	1:8:4
Conversion of propylene, %	40.6	61.9
Degree of conversion of propylene to acetic acid, %	29.0	42.7
Conversion rate of propylene to carbon dioxide, %	8.4	14.2
Degree of conversion of propylene to acetic aldehyde, %	1.0	0
Conversion rate of propylene to acetone, %	2.0	0
Oxidation selectivity to acetic acid, % 71.4		69

Table 2 – Results of the oxidation process of propylene to acetic acid under the given conditions

Temperature	220	320
Pressure	atmosphere	atmosphere
Volumetric rate of the reaction mixture, hour ⁻¹	1500	1500
Propylene:air:water vapor, mole ratio	1:8:4	1:8:4
Conversion of propylene, %	40.6	61.9
Degree of conversion of propylene to acetic acid, %	29.0	42.7
Conversion rate of propylene to carbon dioxide, %	8.4	14.2
Degree of conversion of propylene to acetic aldehyde, %	1.0	0
Conversion rate of propylene to acetone, %	2.0	0
Oxidation selectivity to acetic acid, % 71.4		69

The set of experimental data shows that increasing the partial pressure of water vapor and oxygen has a positive effect on the oxidation process of propylene to acetic acid. However, increasing the partial pressure of propylene decreases the conversion rate of propylene to acetic acid. Based on the conducted studies, the optimal conditions for the oxidation of propylene to acetic acid can be shown as follows:

- volume speed of propylene – 100-150 hours⁻¹;
- propylene: air: water mol. ratios = 1:8:4;
- contact time 1.5 – 2.5 seconds;
- temperature 250 -350 °C.

Under these conditions, the oxidation process of propylene was carried out on a tin-vanadium oxide catalyst, and the results of this study are shown in the table.

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Поступила в редакцию 05.01.2023

Принята к публикации 26.01.2023

Для цитирования:

Mammadov E.E., Rustamova K.M. Study of propylene catalytic oxidation process in a flow-type tubular reactor // Инновационные научные исследования. 2023. № 1-3(25). С. 5-14. URL: <https://ip-journal.ru/>